

Privacy-Preserving Energy Theft Detection Based on Federated Learning

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Abstract—This paper proposes a secure and privacy-preserving framework for detecting unauthorized energy usage by leveraging consumer energy consumption data in smart grids. Addressing the limitations of traditional centralized schemes, a secure privacy-preserving federated learning framework, named Paillier-Encrypted Federated Learning-based Detection (PE-FLD), is adopted. This architecture consists of a global centre and multiple local detection centers, which interact solely with local consumer data and subsequently communicate aggregated parameters to the global center, thereby safeguarding user privacy. Furthermore, a modified Transformer Neural Network is employed for energy theft monitoring in smart meters. Experimental validation is conducted using real energy consumption data from the Irish Electricity Metering Dataset.

Index Terms—Energy theft detection, federated learning, transformer neural network, smart meter, privacy-preserving.

I. INTRODUCTION

Incorporating cloud computing, AI, and 5G enhances grid efficiency and offers energy management benefits through rapid data analysis. However, smart grids face challenges like energy theft, highlighting the need for rigorous detection measures. Machine learning models have been used as a measure for energy theft detection [1]–[5]. Ensemble machine learning models [1], [5], gradient boosting algorithms [2], CNN [3], and an attention-based transformer neural network [4] are some of the models proposed for energy theft detection.

While such machine learning-based methods are capable of accurate detection, the majority of current detection systems transfer and archive energy consumption data in centralized servers, which can violate the privacy of smart meter customers. The imposition of legislative frameworks, exemplified by the 2018 General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) in Europe [6], has underscored the gravity of security and privacy issues. To address these challenges, researchers have pioneered privacy-centric techniques tailored specifically for energy theft detection [7]–[10].

In [7], a convolutional neural network (CNN) model is proposed to analyze reported consumption statistics and identify fraudulent data. Moreover, Paillier encryption is used to encrypt the raw smart measurement data. To detect energy theft and safeguard privacy, a feed-forward neural network and

functional encryption are built up in [8]. However, in these papers, privacy preservation is ensured by processing encrypted consumer data, necessitating intensive computations.

These energy theft detection schemes prioritize user privacy by handling encrypted consumer data directly, leading to significant computational demands. To overcome this issue, federated learning [9] is employed [10]–[12] for energy theft detection. In essence, federated learning facilitates decentralized training, where local models learn from local data and communicate only aggregated parameters to a central entity. This eliminates the privacy concerns related to centralized machine learning by enabling the secure storage of energy usage data. In [10], a decentralized environment consisting of multiple detection stations, control and data centres is established. A federated learning framework is used to train the local detection stations which are based on temporal convolutional networks. A secure protocol is also proposed to secure the parameter exchange between the detection centres and the control centre. In [11], another FL-based decentralized environment with multiple theft detection stations and a central server is established for energy theft detection. In [12], a FL-based decentralized framework utilizing a deep neural network is proposed for intrusion detection in advanced metering infrastructure based on network traffic data. However, any additional security mechanism is used to have secure communication between the detection stations and the central server in [11], [12].

In contrast to existing studies, this paper introduces a robust federated learning framework, named Paillier Encrypted Federated Learning-based Detection (PE-FLD), which leverages Paillier Encryption [13] to enhance energy theft detection with improved privacy and security. By incorporating the Paillier cryptosystem into the federated learning framework, this approach adds an extra layer of privacy protection. The encryption safeguards the machine learning model from potential external threats by securing the model parameters. The Paillier cryptosystem is particularly well-suited for this application due to its compatibility with the mathematical operations fundamental to federated learning, such as weighted averaging.

For the local detection model in the PE-FLD framework, given the cost-efficiency and adaptability of data-driven solutions, this paper adopts a modified TNN, named Convolutional Transformer Neural Networks (CTNN), due to their aptitude for processing time series and capturing long-range features

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in high-dimensional data sequences.

Consequently, motivated by the above studies [7], [10], [14], [15], this paper harnesses the strengths of federated learning, Paillier cryptosystem and CTNN, propelling it to the forefront of secure privacy-preserving, efficient energy theft detection. Therefore, this paper adopts a federated learning framework empowered by the Paillier cryptosystem, Paillier-Encrypted Federated Learning-based Detection (PE-FLD) to address energy theft detection with enhanced privacy and security. In the context of the PE-FLD framework, a modified TNN model called CTNN is employed as a local detection model due to its outstanding performance in handling time-series data. Thorough simulations are carried out using actual energy consumption data to evaluate our proposed approach against state-of-the-art machine learning-based detection techniques.

The remaining sections of the paper are structured as follows: a comprehensive explanation of the proposed approach is given in Section II. A thorough analysis of the outcomes and various performance assessments are provided in Section III. Lastly, Section IV provides the final remarks.

II. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

A. Architecture of the Proposed Framework

The architecture of the proposed framework PE-FLD is illustrated in Fig. 1 which consists of four main components;

Fig. 1. The architecture of the proposed framework

1) *Customer meter*: It is assumed that every customer has a smart meter. The data from these smart meters is gathered at detection centres and analyzed by local detection models.

2) *Detection Centre (DC)*: Let \mathbb{M} be the set of DCs, represented as $\mathbb{M} = \{1, \dots, m, \dots, M\}$. During the model's training process, each Detection Centre (DC) obtains model parameters from the Global Centre (GC). Using these parameters, the DC trains the model on its local dataset, generating local training parameters for the GC. Thus, each DC operates as a local hub for model training and theft detection, optimizing resource usage and enhancing detection capabilities.

3) *Global Centre (GC)*: The GC is responsible for distributing a learning model and default parameters to all DCs during the initial training phase. After each training period, the GC collects aggregated training parameters from the DCs, calculates updated model parameters, and broadcasts these updated parameters back to the DCs.

4) *Key Management Centre*: The Key Management Centre (KMC) employs the Paillier cryptosystem to generate public and private keys. These keys are utilized to encrypt the weights sent from each DC to the GC and to decrypt the weights distributed from the GC to the DCs.

B. FL-based Secure Detection Mechanism

The general training procedure of Paillier-Encrypted Federated Learning Detection (PE-FLD) is outlined in six steps below, with its mechanism detailed in a pseudo-code format in Algorithm 1.

1. Initialization: The proposed framework starts by setting up the global model parameters, including the initial weights ω_c where c denotes the number of communication rounds, at the GC. Simultaneously, the KMC generates public PK and private CK keys using the Paillier cryptosystem [16].

2. Distributing the parameters and keys: After the initialization, the model parameters and generated keys are transmitted from the GC and KMC to each DC. This can be expressed as $\omega_{c,0}^m = \omega_0$ for all M DCs, where $\omega_{c,0}^m$ represents the initial weights of the m -th DC at communication round c and local epoch 0.

3. Local Model Training in each DC: In this phase, each DC trains its local model using its dataset. The model is set up, compiled, and initialized with the weight parameters received from the GC. It is then trained for a defined number of epochs E , using the local data to identify patterns and make predictions. The training process involves a binary cross-entropy loss function f . The resulting weights after training at the m -th DC during the e -th epoch of the c -th communication round are represented as

$$\omega_{c,e}^m \leftarrow \omega_{c,e-1}^m - \eta \nabla f_m(\omega_{c,e-1}^m) \quad (1)$$

where $\nabla f_m(\omega_{c,e-1}^m)$ stands for the gradient of the m -th DC in respect of $\omega_{c,e-1}^m$ and η denotes the learning rate.

4. Encryption of model parameters: Following local training, each client's model weights are encrypted and denoted as $\hat{\omega}_{c,e}^m$, using the public key PK through $Encrypt(\omega_{c,e}^m, PK)$. This encryption safeguards the privacy of the model parameters during parameter exchange.

5. Aggregation of model parameters: After finishing the local training, the DCs send their updated and encrypted weight parameters back to the GC. Upon receiving these parameters, the GC applies $FedAvg(\hat{\omega}_{c,e}^m)$, a technique derived from the Federated Averaging algorithm [9], to aggregate the weights using the formulation provided in (2)

$$\hat{\omega}_{c+1} = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{n_m}{N} \hat{\omega}_{c,e}^m \quad (2)$$

where n_m denotes the number of smart meter measurements at the m -th DC, and M indicates the total number of DCs. N represents the overall number of smart meter measurements aggregated across all DCs. ω_{c+1} refers to the global model weight for the $(c+1)$ -th communication round, which will be distributed back to each DC for the next round of training. This aggregation step ensures that the global model incorporates the combined knowledge from all participating DCs.

6. Local Model Update: Once the aggregation is complete, the GC transmits the aggregated encrypted weights back to the DCs. Each DC then decrypts these weights using the private key CK and updates its local model with $Decrypt(\hat{w}_{c+1}, CK)$.

In summary, each stage plays a role in fostering collaborative knowledge sharing while safeguarding data privacy.

Algorithm 1 Paillier-Encrypted FL based Detection (PE-FLD)

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1: Initialization: global weight parameters  $\omega_0$ , learning rate  $\eta$ , loss function  $f$ , communication round  $c = 0$ 
2: The KMS generates public and private key  $(PK, CK)$  by  $KeyGen$  and send them to each client
3: for  $c \leq C$  do
4:   DC:
5:   for  $m \in M$  do
6:      $\omega_{c,0}^m \leftarrow \omega_c$ 
7:     for  $e \leq E$  do
8:       DC model training:
9:        $\omega_{c,e}^m \leftarrow \omega_{c,e-1}^m - \eta \nabla f_m(\omega_{c,e-1}^m)$ 
10:    end for
11:    DC models' weights are encrypted and sent to GC:
12:     $\hat{\omega}_{c,e}^m \leftarrow Encrypt(\omega_{c,e}^m, PK)$ 
13:  end for
14:  GC:
15:   $\hat{w}_{c+1} \leftarrow \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{n_m}{N} \hat{\omega}_{c,e}^m$ 
16:  GC shares encrypted weight parameters to all DCs
17:  DC:
18:  Each DC decrypts the new weight parameters and updates the local model:
19:   $w_{c+1}^m \leftarrow Decrypt(\hat{w}_{c+1}, CK)$ 
20: end for

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C. CTNN: The Local Detection Model

This section describes the architecture of the CTNN, the proposed model for local detection, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The detection process using this model follows a structured approach, detailed as follows:

Fig. 2. The CTNN model architecture

1) *Data Embedding:* This stage encompasses a CNN model and positional encoding, both enhancing the model's sensitivity to temporal irregularities indicative of energy theft. The first CNN model comprises a one-dimensional convolutional layer (Conv1D) equipped with 128 filters, and a kernel size of 4. This architecture is carefully designed to capture both short-term and long-term temporal patterns, which are essential for detecting anomalies in electricity usage across different time

periods. Following the CNN model, the model employs a positional encoding mechanism to embed sequence information into the inputs.

2) *Transformer Encoders:* The core of the proposed CTNN model's architecture is built around a series of transformer encoder blocks, which are crucial for analyzing time-series consumption data, a key aspect of energy theft detection. Each transformer encoder block consists of the following four essential components:

a) *Layer Normalization Part:* This section begins with a layer normalization operation (LN) that scales and adjusts the input data to improve model stability.

b) *Multihead Attention Part:* The feature extractor, consisting of L layers of identical encoder blocks, is designed to reveal relationships among the encoding vectors of different segments within the load sequence data. Central to this process is the self-attention layer, which enables the model to concentrate on specific segments of the input sequence while producing output for a given position. For each position, the model learns weights that determine the attention given to each input element when generating the output for that position. To enable the model to focus on various types of information across different positions, a multi-head attention mechanism is utilized.

c) *Residual Connection Part:* The initial input is combined with the output from the attention mechanism before being passed to the next segments. This approach addresses two common issues: gradient vanishing and degradation of the weight matrix.

d) *Feed-Forward Part:* In the feed-forward part of the transformer encoder, a Conv1D layer is incorporated into the architecture. Following layer normalization, the Conv1D layer functions as a feature extractor by adjusting dimensionality with f_{dim} and introducing non-linearity through the ReLU activation. This setup delivers a more nuanced understanding of theft patterns, offering greater insight than a conventional multilayer perceptron model.

3) *Global Feature Condensation:* In the global feature condensation process, a global average pooling layer is utilized. This layer calculates the average value of each feature across time, reducing multi-dimensional features from previous steps to a lower-dimensional representation while preserving globally significant information.

4) *Binary Classifier:* The binary classifier utilizes a series of Dense layers with "ReLU" activation functions. To reduce overfitting and improve generalization, dropout layers are strategically placed between the dense layers.

This organized approach enables the CTNN model to effectively learn and make precise predictions, ensuring its effectiveness in the crucial task of energy theft detection.

III. RESULTS

A. Dataset

The dataset from the Irish CER Smart Metering Project [17] is used for evaluation. For computational efficiency, data from 300 smart meters collected over 535 days (approximately 1.47 years) with hourly readings (24 intervals per day) was selected. This dataset is then divided into training, validation, and test

sets with a 6:2:2 ratio. A consistent 6% of samples from each subset are randomly assigned as electricity theft instances, reflecting the dataset's origin from a developed country such as the UK.

B. False Data Injection Attack (FDIA) Types

In this paper, six distinct FDIA models from [18] are employed, each designed for a sample x spanning m days with n time intervals per day. The specifics are outlined in Equation 3, where $f_{1...6}$ represents the six different attack models.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1^d(x_t^d) &= a_t^d x_t^d, a_t^d = \text{random}(0.2, 0.8) \\
 f_2^d(x_t^d) &= \max(x_t^d - b, 0), b < \max(x_{t=1...n}^{d=1...m}) \\
 f_3^d(x_t^d) &= \min(x_t^d, b), b < \max(x_{t=1...n}^{d=1...m}) \\
 f_4^d(x_t^d) &= a_t^d x_t^d, \text{ where} \\
 a_t^d &= \begin{cases} 0 & t_{\text{start}} < t < t_{\text{start}} + \Delta t \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\
 \Delta t &= \text{random}(0.2, 0.8) \cdot n \\
 t_{\text{start}} &= \text{random}(0, n - \Delta t) \\
 f_5^d(x_t^d) &= a \cdot \text{mean}(x_{t=1...n}^d), a = \text{random}(0.2, 0.8) \\
 f_6^d(x_t^d) &= x_{n-t}^d \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

In FDIA-1, throughout the entire period of electricity theft, consumption reports are randomly decreased by a specified percentage. In contrast, FDIA-2 involves reducing all reports by a fixed constant value. FDIA-3 implements a method where consumption reports that exceed a randomly determined threshold are truncated. FDIA-4 designates a random time interval within each day during which reports are replaced with zero values. FDIA-5 employs a strategy where the average consumption from the previous day is reduced by a fixed percentage to generate new reports. Finally, FDIA-6 creates new reports by reversing the order of consumption values from the previous day.

C. Evaluation Metrics

The task of detecting electricity theft at the local detection centre is framed as a classification problem. The positive class identifies entities using unauthorized electricity, whereas the negative class denotes legitimate consumers. The metrics for evaluating model performance, detailed in Equation 4, include accuracy (ACC), false positive rate (FPR), and true positive rate (TPR):

$$\begin{aligned}
 ACC &= (TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN) \\
 FPR &= FP / (FP + TN) \\
 TPR &= TP / (TP + FN) \\
 F1 &= 2 \cdot (\text{precision} \cdot \text{recall}) / (\text{precision} + \text{recall}) \\
 \text{precision} &= TP / (TP + FP) \\
 \text{recall} &= TP / (TP + FN) \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

The F1 index measures the model's ability to accurately and consistently identify customers who are committing theft, defined as the harmonic mean of precision and recall. The true

positive rate (TPR) reflects the model's effectiveness in identifying theft customers without missing any, while the false positive rate (FPR) indicates the extent to which legitimate consumers are incorrectly classified as theft customers.

D. Experiment Settings

All experiments are carried out on a Google Colab Pro Notebook using the NVIDIA A100-SXM4-40GB GPU. The Paillier cryptosystem operations are implemented using the *phe* – 1.5.0 library [16]. Details regarding the cryptosystem components, including key generation, encryption, and decryption, are available in [16].

E. Performance Comparison with State-of-the-art Methods

A thorough study was conducted to evaluate and compare the performance of the proposed Fed-CTNN against state-of-the-art deep learning models within the federated learning framework, including Fed-TNN, Fed-DNN [19], Fed-CNN [20], Fed-LSTM [21], and Fed-TCN [10]. The results are detailed in Table I, and the training accuracy and F1 score values for each model are illustrated in Fig. 3.

TABLE I
COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART MODELS

Model	ACC	F1	FPR	TPR	AUC
Fed-CTNN	95.38	97.51	0.00	88.87	86.47
Fed-TNN	95.01	97.49	0.00	86.43	85.24
Fed-CNN [20]	94.74	97.29	1.64	83.23	84.88
Fed-LSTM [21]	94.24	96.31	0.21	72.65	82.89
Fed-DNN [19]	92.28	94.32	1.96	70.13	81.77

From Table I, it is evident that the Fed-CTNN outperforms the other models in all categories, showcasing its superior capabilities in energy theft detection. Fed-CTNN achieves the highest accuracy, AUC, and F1 score, while also recording the lowest FPR and highest TPR. Fig. 3 further illustrates that the Fed-CTNN model demonstrates superior performance compared to other state-of-the-art models during the training stage as well.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the proposed CTNN and other state-of-the-art models in FLD platform

F. Performance Comparison with Varying Number of Users and Attack Proportions

We explored the impact of different theft percentages—6%, 12%, and 18%—on performance, keeping the dataset size

constant at 100 users per DC. The 6% theft percentage consists of 1% from each of the six FDIAs. By increasing the data modification from each of these FDIAs to 2% and 3%, we achieve total theft percentages of 12% and 18%, respectively. The results are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Fed-CTNN performance under different attack proportions

Fig. 4 shows that as the FDIA percentage increases from 6% to 18%, the Fed-CTNN accuracy decreases by approximately 1%. Nonetheless, the accuracy and F1 score remain above 94% and 96%, respectively, even at an 18% FDIA percentage. The number of communication rounds required for convergence is consistent across all cases, as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Furthermore, investigated data sizes of 100 users, 200 users, and 400 users is investigated, each with a fixed attack strength of 6% on the Fed-CTNN. The results are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Fed-CTNN performance under different user populations

Likewise, Fig. 5 shows that increasing the user base leads to a minor performance decrease of about 1% and 2% when the number of smart meter users per DC is raised from 100 to 200 and 400, respectively. This reduction in performance is likely due to the growing heterogeneity among users as their numbers increase in the DCs.

G. Performance Comparison with Data Imbalance

The allocation of training data across DCs is meticulously designed to reflect real-world disparities. Data is distributed among the four DCs in the following proportions: 10% for DC1, 20% for DC2, 30% for DC3, and 40% for DC4. Each DC is assigned a total of 400 smart meter users according to these proportions. This strategy introduces significant variations in data sizes between some DCs while maintaining uniform sizes in others, thereby offering a thorough evaluation of the federated learning platform's robustness. Moreover, each DC contains approximately 6% of theft incidents. The results for the different DCs are detailed in Table II.

TABLE II
ACCURACY OF DCs WITH VARYING SIZES ACROSS DIFFERENT COMMUNICATION ROUNDS

	DC 1	DC 2	DC 3	DC 4	Avg
Round No.	ACC	ACC	ACC	ACC	ACC
2	95.75	95.63	95.04	94.10	95.13
4	95.68	95.95	95.12	93.96	95.18
6	95.98	95.88	95.35	94.09	95.33
8	96.02	95.85	95.34	94.35	95.39
10	96.02	95.84	95.32	94.35	95.39

Table II reveals that the federated learning framework exhibits considerable robustness, consistently achieving an accuracy of approximately 95% across all DCs. This result highlights the efficacy of federated learning in deriving valuable insights from imbalanced datasets distributed across geographically dispersed DCs.

H. Performance Comparison with Different Number of DCs

This section explores the impact of varying the number of DCs on the performance of Fed-CTNN. We systematically increased the number of DCs from 3 to 10, each with 100 smart meter users, and the resulting performance metrics are detailed in Table III.

TABLE III
FED-CTNN PERFORMANCE UNDER DIFFERENT NUMBERS OF DC GIVEN (SAME DATA SIZE IN EACH DC)

Round No.	3 DCs		6 DCs		10 DCs	
	ACC	F1	ACC	F1	ACC	F1
2	94.34	96.18	94.21	95.98	94.23	96.34
4	94.89	96.91	94.56	96.49	94.47	96.45
6	95.16	96.98	94.89	96.95	94.78	96.82
8	95.35	97.42	94.94	97.05	94.67	96.61
10	95.38	97.51	94.95	97.05	94.67	96.62

Table III shows that while the mean accuracy and F1 score remain consistently above 94% across different numbers of DCs, an increase from 3 to 10 DCs leads to a modest decline in performance. This reduction can be attributed to the growing heterogeneity among the DCs, which results in smaller individual contributions to the aggregated weights during each iteration.

I. Performance Comparison with Different Attack Strength

Evaluating the Fed-CTNN model's robustness against varying and intensified attacks is essential for assessing its resilience. To test this, we adjusted the parameters of FDIA-2 and FDIA-3 in Equation 3, specifically reducing the value of b in f_2 from 0.2 to 0.1 and increasing the value of b in f_3 from 0.15 to 0.25. This modification makes the malicious data more closely resemble normal user consumption patterns, thereby enhancing the subtlety of the attacks and challenging Fed-CTNN's ability to differentiate between nuanced theft and legitimate activities. The FDIA ratio remains at 6% for both standard and advanced FDIAs. The results of this assessment are detailed in Table IV.

Table IV reveals a slight decline in model performance when faced with more sophisticated attacks, where the malicious

TABLE IV
FED-CTNN PERFORMANCE UNDER STRONGER ATTACK STRENGTH

Round No.	Advanced FDIA		Normal FDIA	
	ACC	F1	ACC	F1
2	94.14	96.21	94.34	96.18
4	94.57	96.89	94.89	96.91
6	94.85	97.01	95.16	96.98
8	94.84	96.95	95.35	97.42
10	94.85	96.99	95.38	97.51

data closely mimics normal user consumption patterns. Despite this, the consistently high accuracy and F1 scores across all evaluation rounds indicate that the Fed-CTNN model retains its robustness even under advanced attack scenarios.

J. Performance Comparison with the Secure Communication

We performed a comparative analysis of Fed-CTNN's performance, examining the effects of integrating the Paillier cryptosystem on system efficacy. A 512-bit key size was employed for Paillier Encryption, chosen to balance computational efficiency with security. While larger key sizes generally enhance security, they inversely impact computational speed. The 512-bit key size provides a judicious compromise between these two factors. The results of this analysis are illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Fed-CTNN performance with and without Paillier Cryptosystem

As shown in Figure 6, the overall accuracy and F1 scores remained almost the same, indicating that the integration of Paillier cryptosystem does not affect the Fed-CTNN's performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a modified Transformer Neural Network (TNN) model integrated into a federated learning framework, enhanced by the Paillier cryptosystem, to ensure privacy-preserving and secure energy theft detection. The robustness and resilience of the Fed-CTNN model were validated under diverse operating conditions, including varying attack strengths, different local training data sizes, and various numbers of detection centers. These evaluations highlight the efficacy of the proposed Fed-CTNN model in addressing energy theft detection in a privacy-preserving manner. In conclusion, the CTNN model and the PE-FLD platform provide an advanced, secure, and privacy-compliant solution for energy theft detection within the context of Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI), delivering high performance under a wide range of operating conditions.

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